

A Potential Interpretation of Dark Matter

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Abstract

In this article, the author makes use of simple Newtonian physics without the need for dark matter and Milgrom's MOND theory in order to compute flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies. This approach is justified by the fact, that no dark matter particle has been detected, and also Milgrom's MOND theory has its shortcomings. The gravitational potential energy density serves as the starting point for the calculation, which causes a new kind of gravitational force density, that has not been considered yet. Also a comparison with Milgrom's MOND theory and its shortcomings is made. The author has an explanation why different values for Milgrom's constant are required for agreement with different galaxies' rotation curves. The new approach in the present article therefore yields a potential interpretation of dark matter in the sense, that the latter one is not necessary in order to explain the observed flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies.

Keywords

Newtonian physics, Gravitation, Spiral galaxies, Rotation curves, Dark matter, Modified Newtonian dynamics.

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1. Introduction

Astronomers observe flat rotation curves and exponentially decreasing luminosities with increasing distance from the galactic center of spiral galaxies. This exponentially decreasing luminosity justifies an exponentially decreasing ansatz for the mass distribution for visible matter in spiral galaxies. If one computes and plots the rotation curves with such an exponentially decreasing mass distribution, then one does not get flat rotation curves without any modification like additional invisible matter (dark matter) [1] or using modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND) [2].

But on the other hand, up to now, no dark matter particle has been detected, and also Milgrom's MOND theory has its shortcomings [3, 4]: For instance, different values for Milgrom's constant a_0 are required for agreement with different galaxies' rotation curves.

These are the reasons, why the author has searched for another approach, wherein he makes use of simple Newtonian physics without the need for dark matter and Milgrom's MOND theory. The missing mass problem in spiral galaxies

actually has to be explained with a non-relativistic gravitational theory, because in these celestial objects, the gravitational fields are weak and the velocities are far below the speed of light.

2. Theory

In order to obtain flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies, one takes their gravitational potential energy density [5],

$$\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2}\rho(\mathbf{r})\Phi(\mathbf{r}),$$

as the starting point for the calculation. The intrinsic gravitational potential Φ is generated by the mass density ρ of the regarded celestial object. The intrinsic gravitational force density reads,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{r}) &= -\nabla\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{2}\nabla[\rho(\mathbf{r})\Phi(\mathbf{r})] \\ &= -\frac{1}{2}[\rho(\mathbf{r})\nabla\Phi(\mathbf{r}) + \Phi(\mathbf{r})\nabla\rho(\mathbf{r})]. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Up to the prefactor, the first term in the second line of this equation is the usual, while the second one is the additional gravitational force density, which has some interesting features: Within its intrinsic gravitational potential, a new kind of gravitational force density acts on the regarding inhomogeneous mass density. Like the usual, the additional gravitational force density is attractive because the gravitational potential is a negative quantity, and in celestial objects, the mass density decreases with increasing distance from their center.

2.1 Model for spiral galaxies

The author considers a spiral galaxy as a fluid in the form of an ultrathin axisymmetric exponential disc with the surface mass distribution

$$\Sigma(r) = \Sigma_0 \exp(-r/r_c),$$

where Σ_0 is the central mass density and r_c is the characteristic radius. By replacing ρ with Σ in Eq. (1), the equation of motion in the galactic plane reads,

$$-\frac{1}{2}\left[\Sigma(r)\frac{\partial\Phi(r)}{\partial r} + \Phi(r)\frac{\partial\Sigma(r)}{\partial r}\right] + \Sigma(r)\frac{v^2(r)}{r} = 0,$$

where the last term on the left hand side represents the centrifugal force density. Solving for $v(r)$ yields the equation for the rotation curves of spiral galaxies,

$$v(r) = \sqrt{\frac{r}{2}\frac{\partial\Phi(r)}{\partial r} - \frac{r}{2r_c}\Phi(r)}.$$

By using Toomre's method [6], one obtains the gravitational potential and its derivative multiplied by r in the galactic plane of an ultrathin axisymmetric exponential disc. The formulae at nonzero distance from the galactic center read [5, 7, 8, 9],

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(r) &= -\pi G \Sigma_0 r [I_0(y)K_1(y) - I_1(y)K_0(y)], \\ r\frac{\partial\Phi(r)}{\partial r} &= 4\pi G \Sigma_0 r c_y^2 [I_0(y)K_0(y) - I_1(y)K_1(y)], \end{aligned}$$

while those at $r = 0$ are,

$$\Phi(0) = -\frac{GM}{r_c}, \quad r\frac{\partial\Phi(r)}{\partial r}\Big|_{r=0} = 0,$$

in which

$$M = 2\pi \int_0^\infty dr' r' \Sigma(r') = 2\pi \Sigma_0 r_c^2 \quad (2)$$

is the mass of the spiral galaxy, $y = r/(2r_c) > 0$, and I_n and K_n are modified Bessel functions of the first and second kind, respectively.

In order to study the asymptotic behavior of the rotation curves, one considers spiral galaxies as point-like celestial objects with mass M , cf. Eq. (2), because at large distances from the galactic center, only the monopole contribution of the multipole expansion for the gravitational potential plays a significant role,

$$\Phi_0(r) = -GM/r. \quad (3)$$

Therefore, one obtains for the rotation curve at large distances from the galactic center,

$$v_0(r) = \sqrt{\frac{r}{2}\frac{\partial\Phi_0(r)}{\partial r} - \frac{r}{2r_c}\Phi_0(r)} = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{2r} + \frac{GM}{2r_c}}.$$

Far away from the center of a spiral galaxy, the first term of the radicand becomes small, so that only the constant second one is relevant for the asymptotic behavior of the rotation curve,

$$v_\infty = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{2r_c}}. \quad (4)$$

3. Results

The above presented model for spiral galaxies is used in order to compute their masses and the asymptotic behavior of their rotation curves for different values for the central mass density Σ_0 and the characteristic radius r_c . The results are shown in Tab. 1. The rotation curves of these spiral galaxies and their asymptotic behavior is shown in Fig. 1, wherein all of them are flat. They also show the observed characteristic hump at lower distances from the galactic center. The location of the hump is independent from the central mass density. For lower characteristic radii, the hump appears at lower distances from the galactic center. For the computations, actual values for the physical constants are taken from Ref. [10].

4. Discussion

4.1 Comparison with Milgrom's MOND theory

Milgrom's MOND theory is a modification to Newtonian mechanics in such a way, that it reproduces the Newtonian results at high accelerations. At low ones in the so-called deep-MOND regime, Milgrom's theory features a different

Figure 1. Rotation curves of spiral galaxies. Ultrathick lines are rotation curves with central mass densities $\Sigma_0 = 1500 M_\odot/\text{pc}^2$ while such with $\Sigma_0 = 1000 M_\odot/\text{pc}^2$ are plotted in normal thickness. Solid black lines represent rotation curves with characteristic radii $r_c = 3$ kpc while loosely dash-dotted ones represent such with $r_c = 2$ kpc and densely dashed ones such with $r_c = 1$ kpc. Thin horizontal solid lightgray lines show the asymptotic behavior of the corresponding rotation curve. Their values are listed in Tab. 1.

$\Sigma_0 [M_\odot/\text{pc}^2]$	r_c [kpc]	$M [10^9 M_\odot]$	v_∞ [km/s]
1500	3	84.8	246.6
1500	2	37.7	201.4
1500	1	9.4	142.4
1000	3	56.5	201.4
1000	2	25.1	164.4
1000	1	6.3	116.3

Table 1. The masses of the spiral galaxies, and the asymptotic behavior of their rotation curves which are shown in Fig. 1.

behavior by introducing Milgrom's constant a_0 in order to accord with the observed rotation curves of spiral galaxies without the usage of dark matter [2, 3].

In order to compare the result of the present approach with Milgrom's MOND theory, a spiral galaxy with mass M , cf. Eq. (2), is considered to be point-like. Such an approximation can be made for the comparison, because in the deep-MOND case, one is interested in large distances from the galactic center, where only the monopole contribution of the multipole expansion for the gravitational potential plays a significant role, cf. Eq. (3).

For the comparison with Milgrom's MOND theory in the deep-MOND regime [2, 3], where

$$v_{\text{MOND}}^4 = GMa_0, \quad (5)$$

one powers Eq. (4) by four,

$$v_\infty^4 = \left(\frac{GM}{2r_c} \right)^2 = GMa_0,$$

so that

$$a_0 = \frac{GM}{4r_c^2} = \frac{\pi}{2} G\Sigma_0, \quad (6)$$

what of course is not constant for different celestial objects as presumed in Milgrom's MOND theory. This could be the reason why different values for Milgrom's constant a_0 are required for agreement with different galaxies' rotation curves [3, 4].

But why is a_0 a constant in Milgrom's MOND theory? A possible explanation would be that Milgrom made a fit to a selection of observed rotation curves in order to find an optimized a_0 that is henceforth treated as a constant [2, 3]. Therefore, up to some prefactors, Milgrom's constant can be interpreted as a mean value of the central mass densities from the selection of spiral galaxies for the fit, cf. Eq. (6). Consequently, Milgrom's MOND theory works perfect, when spiral galaxies with nearly the same central mass density are considered, that deviate not too much from those, that were used to make the fit. If this is not the case, different a_0 would be required for agreement with the observed rotation curves [3, 4]. Therefore, if one still uses an unadjusted, fixed a_0 in Eq. (5), then one consequently gets wrong masses for the regarding spiral galaxies from their observed asymptotic rotation curves v_{MOND} .

With this finding, a_0 would have a completely other meaning as originally considered in Milgrom's MOND theory. Moreover, in MOND theory, there occurs another shortcoming: The deep-MOND and the Newtonian regime are incompatible with each other, so that an interpolation function is required for the transition [2, 3]. Such an expedient is not necessary with the theory in the present article.

5. Conclusion and outlook

The author has searched for an approach that is able to overcome the shortcomings of dark matter and Milgrom's MOND theory. Therefore, he makes use of simple Newtonian physics without the need for dark matter and Milgrom's MOND theory in order to compute flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies. The author has an explanation why different values for Milgrom's constant are required for agreement with different galaxies' rotation curves.

If one excludes the existence of dark matter, because so far, no such particle has been detected, then the flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies actually have to be explained with a non-relativistic gravitational theory, as it is done in the present article. The reason for this is, that in this case, the gravitational fields are weak and the velocities are far below the speed of light. Nevertheless, the presented theory in this article also has to be expressed in relativistic form in order to take known relativistic effects into account. Up to now, the approach in the present article is not considered in the theory of General Relativity (GR) at all. Besides, by excluding the existence of dark matter, GR is not able to explain the flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies.

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